

The Controversial Relationship Between China And The United States Of America

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Abstract

This study sheds light on the controversial Sino-American relationship that dates back to the nineteenth century and which developed significantly and may result in a major war, which in the researcher's view is greater than both world wars combined between the two countries or the continuation of the new cold war between them, or an agreement on the principle of interests. Or spare the world a major war according to an ethical legal framework.

1. Introduction

America is a great, great country with a global stature and feared side, and thus it controls the world as it wants. As for China, it is a country tainted by socialism and a huge production machine like it has not been witnessed in history, and its products invaded the new and old world markets. America is a Western country that does not want socialism to penetrate the world. That is why Sino-American relations change. Sometimes cooperation between the two giants is at a high point, and at other times cooperation between America and China is very normal in other areas, and the size of this cooperation depends on time, political climate, global and economic events and the military machine, The relationship between China and America is controversial and controversial.

When we see in terms of the conflict between the two countries, we think that a major war will take place, and when we examine aspects of cooperation, we think that America and China are on a permanent honeymoon. For many reasons, the researcher will review them historically, militarily, socially, economically and securely, which cannot be ignored by the decision-maker easily. Towards more convergence, and the United States is the stronger party that holds the reins of the initiative, even if the scale tends towards more balance. (1) (2)

US-Chinese relations are the question of the future because the great global power and the great global power are cooperating and competing at the same time, especially about whether Beijing will continue to coexist with Washington's military presence in East Asia, or will it make an effort to limit US influence in its backyard? Relations between the two countries ranged between tension and détente, and both of them do not want their relations to reach a dead end, but America is seeking to place it within its strategy, which is based on an attempt to limit Chinese penetration and expansion in Asia and the world. (3) (4)

1.2 Study problem:

Rhetoric and reciprocity reported between the US and Chinese administrations; That there is an unprecedented development in the escalation of old and new differences between the two countries, and the extent of the expected future controversial relationship between the two huge countries depends on the Chinese understanding that America is a great power and dreams at the same time, and the Americans' understanding that China is an inexhaustible productive machine and no one can stop it. Consequently, either coexistence for the sake of common interests or a major war (broader and comprehensive than the concept of the Third World War and with greater devastation than the First and Second World Wars combined) if both countries are considered to be adversaries.

But this dialectical relationship lacks people's knowledge of all its details, especially the inhabitants of the Middle East, and the researcher believes that this knowledge can be accomplished in achieving the following:

- Adequate explanation of the controversial relationship between China and America, and knowing the bright side and the bad side.
- Correct definition of aspects of US-Chinese differences and encounters.

Therefore, the research problem can be crystallized in the following main question: "What is the nature of the dialectical relationship between America and China?"

.1 .3 Study objective:

The study aims to identify the convergences and divergences in the controversial relationship between China and America and a future outlook for it.

.1.4 Importance of the study:

1.4.1 Scientific importance: The study and analysis of the controversial relationship between America and China is one of the most important political topics that require scientific research and investigation in all fields.

1.4.2 Practical significance: striving to provide adequate knowledge of the contentious relationship between America and China; In order to benefit from it in scientific studies, and to improve knowledge of its dimensions; which reflects positively on the way both countries deal with America and China.

.1.5 Previous studies:

1.5.1 The book of (Liu Shih Ching and Li Shi Dong, translated by Abdul Aziz Hamdi, 2003 AD) (5)
China and the United States of America are rivals or partners.

This editorial research book provides a full explanation and exposition of accurate views on Sino-US relations in the political, economic, cultural, military and international security fields. The fluctuations and developments in the Sino-American relations after the end of the Cold War made the governments of the two countries and their societies enjoy a wealth of experiences and lessons regarding bilateral relations, and deepened understanding to some extent regarding the domestic and foreign policies pursued by the two countries. He is keen on the Sino-American relations with a relatively clear and clear knowledge of the areas and problems in which the interests of the two sides fuse, in addition to what are the differences and contradictions between them.

1.5.2 The Study of (David C. Gompert, Astrid StuthCevallos, Cristina L. Garafola, 2016) (6)
War with China thinking through unthinkable

The military confrontation between America and China may reach the severity of devastation to both of them, to East Asia and to the world, which is unimaginable and unacceptable to the mind. However, this is not the case. Beijing and Washington are in conflict over many regional disputes that may lead to a focused or non-focused armed conflict. An orchestrated war between the United States and China is very unlikely, but the threat of poorly managed crises could spark hostilities. Hence, while neither country wants war, the armies of both countries plan to fight. And with the improvement of Chinese capabilities in the systems of preventing access and blocking of areas, the United States can no longer be sure that the war will follow its plan and lead to an overwhelming victory, even though China's losses may be greater than America's losses. This analysis sheds light on various scenarios that a war against China might take and their possible consequences.

1.5.3 The Study of (RashaSuhail Muhammad and Dr. Ban Ghanem Al-Sayegh, 2012) (7)
American policy towards human rights issues in China 1989-2006

The human rights issue is one of the main issues in the Sino-American relations, as Washington uses it as a card to pressure Beijing to force it to respond and update its human rights record and adopt Western capitalist values and concepts according to the American perspective and in a way that serves its supreme national interests.

The issue of human rights emerged in Sino-American relations in the last quarter of the eighties, following the events of the Tiananmen Square that took place in the Chinese capital in May 1989, as China considered it an internal change. America has no right to interfere in its internal affairs and violate its sovereignty and that every country has its own. Freedom to regulate its relations with its subjects according to the nature of its political faith, and that the issue of human rights in China is not necessarily in line with the American concept of human rights. This is because China has its own culture and civilizational legacy, which necessitates it to formulate its internal affairs according to its own perceptions and visions. America has used the human rights issue and raised it from time to time when it was in conflict with its interests with China. America does not seek to achieve humanitarian causes, but rather to pass policies that achieve its interests.

Commentary on previous studies:

It is clear from previous studies the importance of interest in Sino-American relations and the extent of controversy and controversy in these relations. When looking at a certain angle from the analysis of old and current events, one comes to the mind that China and the United States are rivals, but on the contrary, when thinking in another angle, we think that these two countries are partners.

The present study has the advantage that it will present a good presentation on the Sino-US relations, both in the military and in the past; this will help students, soldiers and civilians benefit from it. The research study will also contribute to providing a set of future studies that can cover the deficit in this aspect in the Arab world.

.1.6 Study methodology:

The study adopted the descriptive approach that describes the Sino-US relations in all its aspects by relying on gathering information that helps in describing the problem and analyzing it with the aim of reaching specific conclusions to answer the questions raised by the study.

.1.6 Limitations of the study:

1.6.1 Spatial Limitations: Spatial boundaries extend from East Asia to the Middle East to the New World and all over the world.

1.6.2 Objective Limitations: The study was limited to dealing with the issue of China-US relations.

1.6.3 Temporal Limitations: The study expanded on the time period of the nineteenth century and the time period for preparing this study and the future.

2. The conceptual framework of the study:

2.1 Study concepts and terminology: The study has concepts and terminology that have been simplified to a very understandable extent to all readers.

2.1.1 One Belt, One Road: The New Silk Road adopts the idea of open economic corridors that connect China to the outside world through networks of six corridors, pipelines, gas, oil rails, ports, electric power lines and the Internet because China has a production surplus and is looking for new markets for it for it. Supporting its huge production machine.

2.1.2 Ideology: pumping and transmitting a set of values, concepts, ideas and visions related to a particular ideology in several forms and forms towards an individual or group of individuals, and the goal is to make this individual or group who believes in this ideology.

2.1.3 The Dixie Mission: The Watch Group of the United States Army, whose work continued between July 1944 and March 1947 AD, during World War II, and its goal was to establish official relations with the Chinese Communist Party and the People's Liberation Army.

2.1.4 Strategic information war: stealing information, disrupting networks or achieving damage to them through penetration of computers and information networks of the target country.

2.1.5 The Bamboo Curtain: This is the policy of self-isolation launched by the People's Republic of China in 1949 to isolate the communist Asian countries from non-communists.

3. Historical Roots of US-China Relations (8)

3.1 Beginnings and Containment

The controversial and controversial nature of the US-China relationship passed a long time ago when America entered Asia at the end of the nineteenth century with a different stance from the Europeans. Whereas the European countries were with Japan's endeavor to match it and establish colonies and spheres of influence, the United States in 1899 was calling for an open door policy with China to be open to foreign presence and trade. But an open door also means equality for all foreign powers in their access to China without any leverage. In contrast, Washington disappointed the Chinese nationalists at the Versailles Conference in 1919 when the resulting treaty gave the Shandong peninsula wiped from Germany to Japan, instead of China.

America provided China with generous food aid during the famine in the late 1920s. America supported the republican government in China with leadership when it took control again in its campaign against the local warlords called the marching towards the North during the same period. America supported China and the Republic against Japan during the Pacific War, by sending huge military aid to the hump area, one of the Himalayan mountain ranges and Sichuan.

In the era after 1949 and the founding of the People's Republic of China to succeed the Republicans, General Chiang Kai was applying pressure on and flattering the United States. While Mao Zedong and the Communists were not anti-American, the Korean War (1950-1953), initiated by Stalin at the request of Kim Il Sung and supported by Mao, changed all that, with the implementation of the Chinese policy of self-isolation and the mass anti-American campaigns in the People's Republic of China. . This policy, called the Bamboo Curtain, isolated China, which had entered the Korean War and helped the Vietnamese Communists against the United States, and then came the Korean Armistice in 1953, to spare the two countries the war.

3.2 Blossoming of relationships

Although the alliance between China and the Soviet Union ended between 1959 and 1963; China remained anti-American and still condemned peaceful coexistence, but it was against the influence of the Soviet Union in the Third World. A decade later, the time came to take advantage of the advantages provided by the oppositions between China and the Soviet Union, and America needed China to put pressure on Vietnam and end the war in Indochina. Indeed, Nixon paid a historic visit to China in 1972, accompanied by Henry Kissinger, and met with Chairman Mao to engineer relations between China and America, which were related to Taiwan, the refuge of the republican system in 1949. The two parties, China and the United States, agreed that they would not agree according to the final statement issued. However, the American position on the relationship with China was changing before this date, and thus Sino-American relations flourished, and China was able to invade Vietnam with the tacit approval of Washington to punish the Vietnamese for invading Cambodia. Chinese leader Deng Xiaoping (President of China between 1978 and 1992) visited the United States, where he wore a Texas hat. Nevertheless, Deng did not ally with America, but rather judged each case separately and in line with China's interest. This was followed by his trend towards normalizing relations with the Soviet Union, which were frozen due to regional differences.

3.3 Swipe back to an ancestor

During the election campaign, Ronald Reagan promised that he would defend more Taiwan and criticized his opponent Carter for his weak administration towards China, and tried to increase arms sales to Taiwan during his presidency of America; which angered Beijing. But this controversial relationship between America and China culminated in 1982, when Washington promised to limit arms shipments to Taiwan based on the size of tension and the level of the Chinese military presence in the Taiwan Strait. And it remained like this that every American president criticized his predecessor about not being firm with China until Bill Clinton came when he strengthened trade with China and became a member of the World Trade Organization in 2001, after which China did not object to America's war on Iraq in 2002/2003. This is the biggest evidence of the existence of strategic relations and cooperation between America and China. It should be noted that during the term of President Barack Obama, the shift towards Asia has been greater.

.3.4 Tension in relations, but not at the expense of trade!

In 1996, the United States sent two aircraft carriers to the Taiwan Strait, following Chinese ballistic missile tests. China's declaration of the objection of arms shipments to Taiwan and this is China's proof that it does not accept any thought of accepting the declaration of independence by Taiwan. Relationships have also been strained due to local disputes within China. After the suppression of the Tiananmen Square demonstrations in June 1989 AD, the Group of Seven major industrialized countries approved numerous sanctions, including stopping arms sales to the People's Republic of China, which are still in effect. But these tensions did not affect trade with China, as its trade surplus with the United States reached 345 billion dollars in 2019 AD, and it should be noted that the average monthly imports from China to America 38 billion dollars in the last ten years, and a large part of this investment is directed to buying US Treasury bonds and others. (9) (10)

China delivers a lot on the phrase the basic interests of the two countries, which is the contents of the joint statement during Obama's first visit to China in November 2009, as there are many Chinese issues that need US international support, and we do not forget about China's cooperation in resolving the major financial crisis in 2008.

4. Cold war and issues at stake between China and the USA

Relations between China and America have reached a level of tension that has not been witnessed in nearly half a century, and perhaps the last political skirmish is Washington's directive to Beijing to close its consulate in Houston. Here, we can confirm that there is a cold war between America and China. Many old and new issues are at stake between the two huge states, America and China, which are the fuel for the cold war between them, and the researcher will review them.

.4 .1 Coronavirus (11)

In light of the global Corona virus pandemic, and despite scientists' assertion that the Corona virus is not a factory in laboratories, but rather came from nature, but there is a risk of war behind the scenes between Beijing and Washington. The Americans call the Chinese virus or Wuhan virus on Corona and accuse China of its inaction and was not transparent about announcing what It is taking place at the beginning of the spread of the Corona virus, but the Chinese have strongly rejected these accusations, and there are strong Chinese rumors that an American program for germ warfare is the cause of the great spread of the virus.

Earlier and soon, when the United States announced that it had decided to close its borders to those coming from several European countries, including Italy, the Chinese government announced that it was sending medical teams and necessary materials to Italy, the European country most affected by the epidemic. China also sent aid to Iran and Serbia for the same purpose, and that was a great symbolic moment of transformation, as it referred to the information and propaganda war taking place behind the scenes. China is determined to get out of this crisis and its superpower position. Indeed, the United States is deservedly losing this war at least for the time being.

This fact will not change the recently announced American decision to send a medical clinic belonging to the Air Force to Italy. This is a time when the political and administrative systems of all countries are tested to the fullest extent, and the ability to lead will be necessary, even decisive. The spread of the Corona epidemic threatens to push China-US relations into a more difficult and dangerous stage. This may significantly affect the course of the epidemic's spread and the shape of the world after it recedes. When victory over the virus is declared, the recovery of the Chinese economy will have a vital and important role in the process of rehabilitating the collapsing global economy.

.4.2 Trade War (12)

The trade war between the United States of America and China actually declared itself on July 6, 2018. America applied the first specific tariffs specifically for China, and the Customs and Border Protection Authority collected 25% tariffs on 818 imported Chinese products worth 34 billion dollars. China responded the same day by imposing tariffs of 25% on 545 US-origin goods worth \$ 34 billion. The trade battles between the two sides continued, and there were stages of escalation, de-escalation, negotiations, and Donald Trump's threat to increase tariffs, negotiations failed, and America accuses China of obstructing these negotiations. China claims that it wants mutual benefit and urges America to return to negotiations in the correct manner. It should be noted that these negotiations are very difficult because they are between two different countries in the

financial system, as the administration of China owns companies directly or indirectly, while in America companies depend on the capital financial system. There could be gains for America and China from this trade war. However, if it continues, this will lead to a decline in global economic growth, and the Chinese citizen, as well as the Americans, will be affected by the increase in commodity prices, wages reduction and reduced job opportunities, which has many consequences. (13)

.4 .3 Hong Kong (14)

In 1997, China regained control of Hong Kong, the most important commercial and tourist center, after it was a British colony. Beijing announced the National Security Law to establish a local council of government that strengthens its powers in Hong Kong after mass demonstrations against the prevention of freedoms that were suppressed and the law punished Demands the secession of Hong Kong from China, or acts of sabotage and collusion with foreign powers. In addition to restricting the organization of protests, China actually forces Hong Kong residents to pledge allegiance to it. To spite China for restricting freedoms and undermining the self-rule in it, which China promised the world when it took over this region America ended the US preferential treatment to Hong Kong, as there will be no special economic treatment and it will be large tariffs, and Washington will prevent the export of sensitive technology, and this is an attempt to weaken China and preserve Washington's interests and its hegemony over the South China Sea, which is a strategic area as a hub for trade in the world. (15) (16) (17) (18)

4.4 Uyghur (19)

The Chinese government is accused of committing serious human rights violations in Xinjiang, northwest China, by imposing mass surveillance and detention on more than one million Uighurs, members of the Kazakhs and Kyrgyz ethnicities, or other Muslim minorities, and subjecting them to coercive political ideology, torture, violence, deprivation of food, and denial of religious, cultural and linguistic freedoms. The Trump administration is known to remain silent on the issue of human rights in the world, and America has hinted several times that China will be punished over the Uyghur issue, and in the end, on May 27, 2020. The US Congress almost unanimously approved a bill to impose sanctions on Chinese officials accused of mass arrest of Uyghur Muslims in Xinjiang, as it is one of the rare times that there is party consensus in Congress and Trump only said: We look at this matter closely and the Chinese response was swift. Parliament approved a decision to proceed with the development of national security legislation in Hong Kong. Thus, the American move regarding the Uyghur file comes as one of the cards to pressure China, nothing more. Thus, the rapid move to pay attention to the fate of the Uighurs comes in the context of escalating tension between Washington and Beijing against the background of mutual accusations regarding the Corona epidemic, which Trump calls the Chinese virus.

.4 .5 Taiwan

The Taiwan issue is the most sensitive issue in US-China relations. China considers Taiwan an inalienable part of China, and accepting this is the first condition for China to establish relations with other countries, especially with America. The American political and military presence in Taiwan represents a great challenge and concern to China, which explains this presence and the informal relations that the United States maintains with Taiwan - especially in the field of US arms sales - as carrying fundamental breaches and a complete departure from the agreement between America and China regarding the Taiwan issue since Seventies. China also interprets this as perpetuating the status of Taiwanese secession, and preventing the achievement of unity. This conflict also includes displays of force with the US Navy from time to time. Given the periodic tensions over Taiwan and the growing military power of China, the clear statements of Chinese leaders and the provocative statements of Taiwan leaders, and some evidence of increasing nationalism and the possibility of miscalculation, whether in China, Taiwan, or the United States, may be a potential cause of conflict between the United States and China, it should be The war on Taiwan is taken very seriously. (21) (22)

.4 .6 South China Sea

Relations between Beijing and America have been strained over the South China Sea, a waterway rich in resources and causing political confrontations in the region. China affirms its entitlement to most of the sea in which it built artificial islands to enhance its power in the region. China has been accused of deploying warships, arming those islands it has built, and stopping fishing vessels that angered its neighbors. While the US warships are carrying out exercises under the name of freedom of navigation at sea, and sailing near the landmarks that China asserts their right to, which anger China and increases tensions. (23)

.4.7 Peninsula Korean

The common strategic interests between Washington and Beijing on the Korean Peninsula formed a fertile environment in US-China relations, due to considerations related to regional and global influence and hegemony. The two countries are the primary forces in determining and maintaining peace conditions. Therefore, the form that a unified Korea can take will be of interest to both countries at the same time, and this was already evident in the year 1950 when tension gradually increased under the slogan of unifying the two parts by force and the war broke out between the two Koreas. America, its Western allies, and United Nations forces intervened on the side of South Korea, and in return China and Russia intervened with their forces on the

side of North Korea. Consequently, this issue produced an atmosphere of direct conflict between Beijing and Washington on this battlefield, in addition to the direct and implicit statements of Chinese leaders referring to its military intervention in the event that the United States interferes in the Korean issue in a non-peaceful manner, as China's interest in return lies in the continuation of the status quo on the peninsula.

The Korean government, as required by the strategic interests of China, does not want the establishment of a strong, unified neighboring Korea, with military might, possibly nuclear, and allied with the United States. China is also trying to exploit the nuclear file of North Korea as a card in favor of managing its relations with America, especially since China is the only party most influencing the external behavior of North Korea, and this is mainly due to the financial aid it provides and its willingness to protect the nature of the existing military and political system in Korea. In addition, China needs a buffer for its security that corresponds to the US alliance with Japan and South Korea, and this is relatively what North Korea embodies. (24)

.4 .8 Intellectual Property

Americans focus greatly on China and intellectual property rights, as Washington believes that China's practices in recent years threaten the United States' economy, and strong technical and intellectual property protection must be required, because China is carrying out tactics in which it violates the great values of intellectual property of America by actively lobbying the Chinese on American investors. In China, for the participation of Chinese companies, which in turn reach the intellectual property of America. Also, Americans believe that when American intellectual property owners are allowed to license their technology in China, they must do so under discriminatory regulations that have prevented American intellectual property owners from receiving market rate returns.

The Americans also believe that China has implemented foreign investment programs to obtain American intellectual property through the acquisition of targeted American companies. The Americans talked about the frequent computer breaches of commercial networks in the United States, indicating that the Chinese government targeted confidential business information and other sensitive data for American companies, despite pledges not to do so. In addition, China's policies have effectively deprived US companies of the full value of their intellectual and technical property, and to some extent prevented them from competing in the large Chinese market. In addition to the above, Americans believe that the main trading partners of the United States have shown little willingness to take practical steps to pressure China on these issues. Washington expresses its fear of the fact that many countries have transferred their production to China, and thus losses in technical and intellectual property will increase, and all this in the interest of China at the expense of America. (25)

.4.9 Cyber security

There have been two major revolutions in the history of humanity, the industrial revolution between the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries, which resulted in a new world order, and the other revolution is the technology and information revolution in our days, which resulted in strategic information warfare and its main weapon is information that meets the strategic goals of countries. Advanced and others. Consequently, cyber security has become the main concern of Washington, which considers it the greatest threat to its national security coming from Beijing, which is acquainted with military secrets and commercial information related to the United States of America, while directing cyber-attacks that disrupt the electronic system of defense and intelligence networks. It is considered one of the most important new changes affecting US-China relations, due to the fact that possessing technical and cognitive strength is an additional force for the elements of the comprehensive state power in the twenty-first century. (26)

.4. 10 The 5G Communication Spree

The signs of a third world war called the technological war may result from the 5G technological Spree that is being watched by all the inhabitants of the earth nowadays, which will affect the global economy. It has the characteristics of the accelerated and strong competition in the development of fifth generation networks because of its huge capabilities that will provide it to all sectors, and the Chinese company Huawei is the largest giant on the throne of these networks. These new welcomed and criticized networks at the same time have led to Washington's concern about the expected Chinese progress in the economy and in military affairs as well as politically because it will be in control of information security.

This prompted the US government to disrupt the development of this network from the Chinese side and adopt plans to develop this network to counter Chinese espionage, as Washington launched two major attacks targeting Beijing and the largest Chinese company, Huawei, the technology giant, as it is the company that is the focus of US attacks, being the largest Chinese technology company. Innovative and competitive on the global level, made it a symbol of Chinese technological rise. Huawei is under severe scrutiny after it was blacklisted by the United States, which urges its allies not to use Huawei technology to build the fifth generation of communications networks due to fears that this company is a tool used by China to spy and thus threaten the national security of America and its allies. (27)

5. A military comparison between China and America (28)

China, which developed militarily after the mid-nineties of the last century, with its military capabilities less than America, its modest capabilities in the field of aircraft carriers, and its possession of an advanced air

and coastal defense network, can retreat the latter forces in Asia, which possesses many aircraft carriers, despite the reduction in Washington's military capabilities after the war. Cold, but it retained the advantage of speedy arrival of its forces to any place in the world and the completion of tasks while not exceeding the ability of China in military domination of East Asia and the farthest point of its ports of Yemen to protect against piracy. More than half of China's fourth-generation aircraft are integrated with early warning aircraft and have less than two thousand short-range ballistic missiles with a ratio of less than five meters, and within their range is Okinawa, specifically the American air base Kadena in Japan.

Despite the ability of the American forces to control the war if it extended to defend Taiwan against China, there is a fear from experts that it will be a complicated and costly matter for America as the American forces will remain exposed to Chinese planes and the American air fighters will have to travel long distances to strike the Chinese forces. This poses difficulties for the United States' ability to penetrate Chinese territory. With the increasing risk of penetrating the Chinese field, the availability of the existing Joint Direct Attack Munitions and the long-range confrontation weapons; some advantages of the United States in the backyard of China. The simulation of the attack on the forty Chinese air bases with fighter jets from Taiwan without refueling showed that the ability to close the take-off corridors at these bases diminished from eight hours in 1996 to three days in 2010, and expectations of this will remain stable until 2017.

In 1996, the United States had two aircraft carriers in front of Taiwan, and that was a deterrent to China. Today, however, China possesses modern missile capabilities against ships, which have made those carriers in an awkward position. Although the US forces possess anti-missile weapons, the growing Chinese capabilities in the fields of intelligence, military satellites, surveillance, submarines, advanced torpedoes and cruise missiles, place additional burdens on US forces in the region. And the American forces have so far prevented their Chinese counterpart from landing on Taiwanese soil, despite China doubling its amphibious forces and airbag carriers since 1996 and developing its helicopters and anti-submarine ships. The US submarines and the air force have the potential to inflict losses on the Chinese force by about 40% in seven days of operations, which means destroying the organizational integrity of the landing forces.

It should be noted that China has increased its dependence on satellites. And there were worrying signs of Beijing's trend towards making anti-space weapons, which prompted the United States to start financing some anti-satellite equipment in 2002. However, the danger remains due to China's reliance on some clandestine networks on the Internet. China does not have the ability to prevent the United States from absorbing the first strike and directing a second blow to Beijing. America outperforms China in the number of nuclear warheads by a ratio of 13 to 1. And it has become necessary for Western governments to explain to China the enormous risks of aggression, and that they should not exaggerate in The ability of its forces to control and rule over the conflict. China should also be involved in issues of establishing strategic stability and preventing escalation. (29) (30)

6. US-China Relations in the Middle East, Africa and Latin America

The advancement of China's growth has fueled competition with the United States of America in several areas. China has expanded its economic, political and military relations with the Middle East and adopted the strategy of defending the distant seas by seeking to increase the size of its naval presence in the Middle East. Consequently, it has become a new international player in the region to increase China's dependence on its oil and not leaving America unique in the region. Washington is concerned about the commercial and technological dealings between China and Israel, as it opposed China's purchase of spy planes from Israel in 2000, and America was apprehensive about the construction of the Haifa Port by China, fearing that it would have intelligence and military implications and increase Beijing's influence.

Washington do not forget the Sino-African economic partnership, where trade exchanges reached nearly \$ 190 billion in 2016, according to the declaration of the China-Africa Forum for Investment in Morocco in 2017, and Beijing was attacked by Washington through its talk of vague agreements and strategic exploitation that make African countries meet China's demands and loans. A brutal Chinese that prevents growth in Africa, and China feeds African crops and does not increase job opportunities, as America believes that the Chinese economic initiative is one belt or one road, which is the new Silk Road and a way to extend Chinese influence globally, and build a military base in the Horn of Africa, specifically in Djibouti Near the US base, and is using its economic influence to control African ports. The Chinese presence also appeared in the back garden of America through Chinese loans and large investments to Latin American countries and America closely following these developments with investments that modify China's investments in Africa, and come second to the size of investment after America in the region. (31)

7. American-Chinese mutual dependency:

The aspects of US-Chinese cooperation are many, and there are mechanisms from both countries to manage their complex and controversial relationship, as the two countries 'economies are mingled through commercial transactions, investing money and granting loans, which in turn alleviate the weight of the difference between Washington and Beijing. America designs products, China manufactures them, America and the world consume these cheap products, knowing that the Chinese profits from this trade are invested in

America, which led to saving expenditures on the American citizen as well as providing him with more jobs and thus there is an integrative relationship between America and China, especially the purchase of American debt.

We can conclude that they are partners or subordinate to each other almost, as America and China import from each other in very large numbers in addition to the large amount of financing of US debt by China. So the preference of large commercial interests over political interests is inevitable and strategic partnership is better than the reality of competition. In fact, the Chinese and American presidents agreed during the G20 summit in the last quarter of 2019 AD on appeasement and negotiations regarding the trade battle and what follows it. The two countries are continuing to cooperate on a wide range of issues. China is pressuring North Korea to take moderate positions, and America is concerned with the fate of the Chinese Muslim Uyghur extremists in Syria. Despite US support for Taiwan, it does not support independence as an option for voters on the island. America also accepted China's efforts to obtain energy resources and raw materials, and even opened the way for Chinese investments in this field.

However, this mixture of competition and cooperation is what can be expected of two great powers, who have divergent interests but also have great interdependence. However, it seems that the divergence between the political values between them is the basis for a turbulent situation in which there is economic cooperation and integration, the manifestation of which is the condemnation of the oppressive Chinese regime regarding freedom of expression and its continued denial of the right to self-determination in Tibet, in addition to criticizing its international policies, especially with regard to Iran. (32)

8. Compliment nations with the same interest:

The Chinese people focus on teaching children courtesy and therefore they are a courteous people of the first order. And Americans focus on this also and therefore in their nature will not look to war as a first choice. America and China are fully aware of the strong and common causal relationship between the two countries in sustainable economic growth, public and private investment and economic growth. They also know that the US tariffs on China are economically harmful to both countries, and that both countries will tend to peace and reject and manage differences in the interest of common interests. (33) (34) (35)

9. Findings and Recommendations:

After we finished studying the China-America relations, we reached some results and Recommendations, perhaps the most important of them the following:

After many years of self-imposed retreat, China launched after the Cold War with dreams of a multipolar world.

Based on America's belief that a country will emerge on the scene and its competition for the unipolar throne in the Arctic, America will search for real economic partners, including China, and it will remain the strongest America in the world.

- The preoccupation of professional researchers has occupied the future of Sino-US relations and their thorny files; will it be a major war or cooperation?

What will be the consequences of America's provocation of the world's high-growth China?

- China wants to cooperate in marketing its products.

- Full image, North America, North America.

10. Future studies:

- Trade in Chinese dragons and American cowboy.

- The great challenge for China to enter the international community and America's acceptance of it as a democratic country.

- US-China Relations as an academic course for students of economics and political science.

- The impact of the Corona pandemic on China's relationship with America.

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